

Inclusive and Equitable Education

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Abstract

Inclusive education aims to ensure that all children, regardless of background or ability, receive quality learning in supportive environments. However, in Nepal's Madhesh Province, significant barriers impede this goal. Challenges include inadequate teacher training, irregular student attendance, and limited use of student-centered methodologies. Overcrowded classrooms, poor infrastructure, and unsafe learning conditions exacerbate disparities. Social norms, gender biases, peer violence, and discrimination against children with disabilities further hinder inclusion. Additionally, inactive School Management Committees (SMCs) and political interference often obstruct effective policy implementation, neglecting marginalized students' needs.

Educational assessments such as NASA, NARN, and EGRA reveal critical learning deficiencies: grade 3 students correctly solve only 43.5% of reading and 37.2% of numeracy problems, with just 20% of children in grades 2–3 possessing foundational literacy and numeracy skills. Early Childhood Care and Development (ECCD) enrollment is insufficient, with only 62.9% of grade 1 entrants in Madhesh having ECCD experience, below the national average of 76.7%. Promotion rates are particularly low among marginalized groups, including Dalits and Muslims.

To address these challenges, World Vision International Nepal's SIKAI Project in Sarlahi district prioritizes equitable education for vulnerable children. The project integrates child-centered teaching, inclusive pedagogy, and supplementary learning materials while improving school infrastructure, including Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) facilities. Assistive devices such as glasses, rollators, CP chairs, and hearing aids have been provided to 289 children with disabilities, enhancing their educational access. Furthermore, 600 out-of-school children received educational materials to facilitate their transition into formal schooling.

Sustainable policy reforms and collaborative efforts among government, communities, and development partners remain essential to ensure that no child is left behind and that inclusive education becomes a reality in Madhesh Province.

Keywords: inclusive education, marginalized groups, child-centered teaching, formal schooling, educational equity